

ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS IN KARSHI CITY

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the basis of historical sources about historical architectural monuments and shrines located in the Kashkadarya oasis, in particular in the city of Karshi.

The Kashkadarya oasis has long been one of the centers of sedentary agriculture and urban planning. There are 638 archeological monuments, 181 architectural monuments, 37 shrines, 75 sculptural monuments in the region.

Kokgumbaz mosque (16th century), ancient bath (16th century), ancient bridge over Kashkadarya (16th century), Sharofboy madrasah (early 18th century), Charmgar mosque (mid-19th century), Bekmir madrasah (1905), Khoja Abdulaziz madrasah in Karshi (1907), Kilichbek Madrasah (19th century) and other architectural monuments have been preserved[1].

We will discuss the architecture of Karshi on the basis of the monuments that

have survived to the present day, categorizing them according to their functions, as well as the architectural structures that existed and studied a quarter of a century ago[2].

The bathhouse in Karshi in the 16th century is a classic example of this type of medieval construction, and such ancient baths are rare in Central Asia. M. Masson confirms the existence of a legend that connects the construction of this bath with the name of Abdullakhan II, and considers it built in 1592-1593[3].

The bathroom is rectangular in shape (22 by 14.4 meters) and has five rooms long and three wide. The rooms are arranged around a central hall with a large dome (5.6 meters high). From the modern

above-ground device, the stairs lead down to the main semi-underground part of the bathroom. Here the temperature rose inwards.

One of the unique surviving structures of this type in Central Asia is the bridge over the Kashkadarya in the XVI century. It is built of multi-layered brick. The bridge rests on twelve strong piers connected by fourteen wide and low arches. The length of the bridge is 122 meters, width - 8.2 meters, height in the central part from the riverbed to the road surface - 5.35 meters. Between the arches, the piers, installed on both sides of the bridge, are 4 meters in diameter, the base is expanded with stone blocks and reinforced with powerful counterparts in the form of cylinders.

Over time, the riverbed widens, requiring the bridge to be extended and repaired. As a result, in 1914, additional sections were built on both sides of the bridge, and two brick guards were built at the entrance. They were demolished in 1970 for obstructing freight traffic. Later, a new bridge was built and the old one was almost never used, that is, it was preserved as a historical structure. In 2005, the guardhouse was rebuilt[2].

There were three traditional types of mosques in Movarounnahr: neighborhood mosques for the local population, where prayers are offered five times a day; Mosques for city prayers on Fridays: Eid mosques - prayer halls (idgoh, musalla). Eid mosques are designed for men in and around the city to pray twice a year - on Eid al-Fitr and Eid al-Adha. One of the few surviving mosques in Central Asia, the Kokgumbaz, built in the 16th century, has survived in Karshi.

The mosques of the time were built with a high arch in the center and an altar in the west. There is usually a square in front of the complex, which is designed to accommodate men living in and around the city during Eid prayers. They were mostly built outside the city because there had to be space around it. The mosque in Karshi was built in a similar way. The building was built on the outskirts of the city in the 16th century, and over time, as the city expanded, it remained in the city center. This mosque was the largest and most majestic of its kind in Movarounnahr.

The part of its rectangular history (38, 25 by 14.6 meters) with an arched altar on the west side was pushed forward. The composition of the building is distinguished by its arched middle part and a high dome and roof. It is connected to it by two descending wings on both sides.

Each has a gallery with four domes and a single column in the center, with two ridges opening towards the central hall, as well as the head and side facades.

The low foundations (0.7 to 1.1 meters) are made of fine brick with a clay mixture. The walls and large columns of flowers are made of baked brick. The central hall is covered with a two-tiered dome. The inside of the domes is mounted on the porch, the outside is decorated with a decorated Blue Dome-high drum - mounted on the pedestal. That is why it is called the Blue Dome. The drum is decorated with Islamic patterns, which can be read from afar. He repeats the Arabic saying, "Eternity belongs to Allah." It is followed by another Arabic phrase in small letters, "Glory to Allah"[4].

The main decoration is inscribed on the main arch, using a continuous mosaic typical of that period. Glazed patterns used

white, blue, blue and turquoise. The words "Allah", "Muhammad", "Bakht" are inscribed on the flat surface of the roof with glazed tiles. There is a star-shaped picture on the side of the roof. Here on the glazed roof one could read the inscription "The building was built in 999 AH (1590-1591 AD) according to the supreme decree of Abdullah II". Here the name of the architect of the mosque is written Mir Boqi Bahodir.

The construction of the Abdullah II madrasah in the Karshi region is also connected with his name. It is the name of a man named Beki Biy, who was honored by Abdullakhan for saving his life.

Initially, the altar and walls in the interior of the mosque were glazed. Together with the dome, which collapsed in the late 19th century, they were rebuilt in the late 20th century during a major overhaul of the building.

The neighborhood mosques are traditionally numerous, built in the center of almost every neighborhood, and are designed for five daily prayers. Near the neighborhood and village mosques, which are the main structures of the community center, there is often a courtyard, which has a bathroom, toilet, sometimes a bathhouse, a school, several rooms, a coffin, a pool. The neighborhood mosques had a domed, columnar or columnless yassitom hall. They are surrounded on two sides, or often on three sides, by a canopy with wooden columns.

Among the surviving mahalla buildings in Karshi, the most powerful was the Chakar Mosque. It had a hall with a rectangular, six-column, introverted composition, surrounded by a porch on three sides. There are four doors leading from the hall to the porches, two doors in

the front, and an altar on the west side. The hall had an altar decorated with antique details, carved columns, doors, chain ganch pattern. The building is made of baked brick, the level of which, including the porches, is 22x22 meters, the level of the hall - 11.5x15.7 meters.

Built around the 19th century, the Mahallot Mosque is a four-column hall with a three-sided porch and adjoining walls. The central part of the mosque's wooden beamed roof is slightly raised in the shape of a pool and is decorated with blue, red, and green watercolors. Including the porches, the size of the building is 22.5x14 meters, the hall is 10x10 meters. The bricks of the poly are arched in the shape of an arch.

Buzruk Obod Mosque dates back to the XIX century and its walls are built in the form of a double. The mosque is located in the center of the district, with a swimming pool and a gate. The area of the complex is 17.5x22.5 meters, the hall is 7.5x9.3 meters.

One of the mosques in the Gumbazli neighborhood is the Khoja Ahror Mosque. Here the domed hall is connected on both sides by a porch with wooden columns and a roof mounted on columns. The dome of the square-shaped hall of the mosque, made of baked brick, is mounted on arched arches in the corner. In the south-eastern part of the building there is a brick staircase leading up to the level of the dome. The patterns of the preserved doors and wooden bars and porch pillars date back to the XIX-XX centuries. Including the awnings, its size is 12.6x12.8 meters.

The pottery mosque was built in the early 19th century in the pottery district of the old city. In its square were several rooms and a gate, and an incredibly

beautiful century-old mulberry tree. The synchronized building of the mosque consisted of a rectangular-shaped hall 6.2x 6.8 meters, with a columnar porch connected to it from the south and east, and a rectangular-shaped building entered by a southern porch. The glazed patterns of the building have not been preserved [5].

About ten of the twenty madrasas known in 1920 have survived in the city of Karshi in the 1970s. These madrasas were characterized by the following general features: the walls of buildings of the XVIII-XIX centuries were made of three layers of traditional Muslim baked bricks, the inside was filled with brick fragments and construction waste mixed with a mud mixture; the walls are covered with small-sized polished bricks assembled by means of a gypsum mixture; the rooms are covered with balkhi-style ceilings; there was an entrance to the rooms from the corner of the courtyard; the main corridor leading through the vestibule led directly to the inner courtyard without the traditional side corridors; the sides and backs of the building were flat and unadorned; the main entrance is decorated with flat arched shelves, all the buildings are single-storeyed, and only the large madrasas have two-storeyed entrances to make the building look more dignified.

One such building was the Shermuhammad Madrasa (which has not yet been preserved). It is a symmetrical building with a straight rectangular shape (27.5x24.6 meters), the main facade is two-storey, the rest is one-storey. The roof and side wings of the building are decorated with flat shelves, and in the corners of the main entrance there are towers-bouquets, which are finished with an arched lantern.

Khoja Qurbon Madrasah (which has not reached us) is a rectangular (21.25x21 meters) building with a small courtyard (10.7x9.1 meters), surrounded by rooms with ceilings. The only domed hall at the entrance was the classroom, and the second hall was replaced by two rooms, as a result of which the lobby was separated from the central axis. The unevenness of the entrance affected the front of the building, and the number of arches on the sides of the portal remained uneven[6].

The Sharof Khoja Madrasa, according to local sources, was built in the early 18th century by its teacher Sharof Khoja. It is a small, rectangular, symmetrical building with a small courtyard. The summer mosque on the west side of the courtyard has a wooden porch, which is a rare occurrence. It is known in some monuments of the XVIII century. The exact time of the construction of these three madrasas is not known. According to some reports, L.Yu. Mankovskaya believes that the first of them (Shermuhammad madrasah) was built in the XVII-XVIII centuries, and the other two in the XVIII-XIX centuries[7].

Bekmir Madrasah (28.07x28.57 meters) built in 1903 and Abdulaziz Madrasah (26x21 meters) with a rectangular shape built in 1909 are among the largest and closest to the classical form. While the main part was one-story, the front and entrance were two-story. Their mutually similar roof pieces are single in the center, the second floor of the side wing has an arched gallery, and in the corners of the building there are bouquet towers with lights on top. In the Abdulaziz madrasa, an arched lamp is decorated with a purple-patterned air-colored dome.

The Kilichboy madrasah of the early twentieth century has a similar architectural solution. The building is rectangular in shape (17.2x19.8 meters), the main facade is two-story, but the decoration is a bit darker.

Some one-story madrassas continued to be built of traditional rectangular bricks based on clay mixtures. The Jumaboy madrasa, which has not yet arrived, was built in the same way. This building was built in the first decade of the XX century at the expense of a local rich man, according to local people, by

Samarkand craftsmen. The building was a rectangular shape (20.9x18 meters), the composition of the facades was uneven.

In short, most of the architectural monuments of the XVI-XIX centuries in Karshi have survived to this day. Among them are the bridge built by Abdullakhan II, Kilichboy madrassah, Kokgumbaz mosque, Odina mosque, Abdulazizkhan madrassah, Bekmir madrassas. In general, most of these facilities have been renovated by the state in recent years.

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